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THE GDPR IN SPACE: MAPPING JURISDICTION AND NAVIGATING TRUST

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the applicability of Article 3 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to space-based personal data collection conducted via Earth observation satellites. Moreover, it measures these findings against public trust perceptions and privacy attitudes. The research adopts a multi-methodological approach, combining a legal doctrinal analysis with psychological theory. Furthermore, it conducts semi-structured interviews with several subject-matter experts. The legal analysis highlights the GDPR's potential but ambiguous extraterritorial reach in regulating these instances. In parallel, the psychological dimension reveals low public trust in space-based observation satellites, compounded by technical complexities and a growing sense of dependence. In order to integrate the two dimensions and create constructive suggestions, this article applies Malcolm Sparrow's risk framework. This reveals that, despite legal uncertainty, the risks associated with satellite-based personal data collection by observation satellites necessitate regulatory oversight, positioning supervisory authorities in a key role for addressing societal harms that extend beyond formal legal responsibilities.

“I often see privacy set against innovation or law enforcement efforts. But privacy is also a form of security, equally important as protection from crime.”

– Monique Verdier, Deputy Chair of the Dutch DPA²

KEYWORDS: GDPR, Extraterritorial Scope, Space-based Satellite Surveillance, Trust Perceptions, Risk Management.

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² Author interview with Monique Verdier (Deputy Chair Dutch DPA), 2 June 2025.

1. INTRODUCTION

Personal data breaches have become global risks rather than isolated incidents, affecting millions of people.³ A personal data breach is an event involving unauthorised access, disclosure, or misuse of personally identifiable information by someone without proper authorization or for an improper purpose.⁴ Traditionally, personal data breaches have occurred via Earth-based systems, such as subsea fibre-optic cables or wireless networks.⁵ With the growing dependence on outer space satellites for the transmission and storage of data, there is a notable shift in the risk landscape. In the contemporary era, space-based personal data breaches appear increasingly inevitable.⁶

Within this evolving context, a critical legal question arises concerning the applicability of the *General Data Protection Regulation* (GDPR) to personal data processed beyond the Earth's surface. As complex technological capabilities expand into outer space, the need for explicit legal safeguards becomes more pressing.⁷ Moreover, it is essential to approach this matter not solely from a legal perspective but to adopt a broader socio-psychological lens that considers the wider implications. That is because the societal impact of space-based personal data processing extends beyond what legal frameworks can address alone. Moreover, public perceptions determine not only how society views these privacy issues but also how such matters ought to be addressed. Therefore, this article explores the potential applicability of the GDPR to personal data collection by space-based observation satellites and critically examines how this aligns with public trust perceptions in personal data protection in space.

Satellites have become an indispensable part of daily life, supporting a wide range of critical functions across modern society.⁸ The world grows increasingly dependent on satellites and space-based systems for surveillance, infrastructure, communication, and numerous other essential functions. Therefore, understanding their role in relation to privacy concerns is crucial for ensuring ethical governance, public trust, and the protection of individual rights in an era of expanding technological dependence.⁹ There are fundamentally different types of satellites, each with distinct technical properties. While some are capable of storing data over extended periods, others are limited to real-time data transmission.¹⁰ Accordingly, this study narrows its analytical scope to observation satellites.¹¹

³ Leyden, J., Swinhoe, D., & Hill, M. (2024, September 12). *The 18 biggest data breaches of the 21st century*. CSO Online. <https://www.csoonline.com/article/3257425/the-18-biggest-data-breaches-of-the-21st-century.html>.

⁴ Kyriazoglou, J. (2024, October 25). *Information security and breach definitions and obligations*. Apress. 1–14. https://doi.org/10.1007/979-8-8688-0870-8_1.

⁵ European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA). (2020, December 14). *ENISA threat landscape for 5G networks report*. <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-threat-landscape-report-for-5g-networks>.

⁶ Peeters, W. (2022). *Cyberattacks on satellites: An underestimated political threat*. LSE IDEAS, London School of Economics and Political Science. <https://www.lse.ac.uk/ideas/projects/space-policy/publications/Cyberattacks-on-Satellites>.

⁷ Zoltick, M. M., and Colgate J. L. (2019). *The application of data protection laws in (outer) space*, 6–11.

⁸ Huang, H., Guo, S., and Wang, K. (2018). Envisioned Wireless Big Data Storage for Low-Earth-Orbit Satellite-Based Cloud. *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 25(1). <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWC.2018.1700178>.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Sergieieva, K. (2025, March 22). *Types of satellites: Different orbits & real-world uses*. EOS Data Analytics. <https://eos.com/blog/types-of-satellites/>.

¹¹ The technical rationale for this focus follows in the literature review.

The GDPR represents one of the most significant advancements in personal data policy.¹² However, its enforcement regarding space-based personal data collection is sometimes contested due to ambiguous outer space jurisdiction.¹³ A recent report highlights that the extraterritorial enforcement of the GDPR remains uncertain when entities operate outside EU territory without an establishment, representative, or assets within the Union.¹⁴ Although various legal frameworks may be relevant for addressing personal data collection or processing in outer space, this article concentrates on the GDPR, given both its foundational role in European data protection, its global informal influence, and the necessity of maintaining a focused scope.¹⁵

The legal and psychological dimensions of this research are profoundly interconnected. Legal frameworks outline rules for personal data protection, yet their societal influence and necessity arise from perceptions of people.¹⁶ Following this, the academic relevance of this study lies in its dual contribution: it provides a doctrinal legal analysis exploring the potential applicability of the GDPR to space-based observation satellites, and also examines how it corresponds with European citizens' perception of the protection of their personal data in space. This dual approach creates a novel and meaningful combination.

Towards the end of the article, the analysis weighs these two dimensions against each other: the legal reality versus public perceptions and concerns. This leads to an evaluative and normative conclusion, showing that the GDPR, as current legal protection, is not entirely sufficient. However, it should be, given citizens' concerns and their low trust in existing data governance frameworks. As a suggestion, this article introduces the national supervisory authority as a key factor in overseeing compliance and addressing emerging risks.

2. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This article answers a central research question, which it explores through two sub-questions. It adopts a dual methodological approach: a legal doctrinal analysis of the GDPR to space-based observatory satellites, and theoretical research into public trust and attitudes regarding personal data protection in observatory space technologies. Additionally, the research included four interviews with subject-matter experts to substantiate the findings.

- I) The central research question of this study states: How does a possible application of Article 3 of the GDPR to personal data at space-based observation satellites intersect with the trust attitudes of European citizens regarding personal data protection in space?
- II) The first sub-question of this study pertains to the legal dimension, stating: To what extent does the extraterritorial scope of Article 3 of the GDPR apply to personal data collected by Earth observation satellites operated by entities falling within its jurisdictional scope?
- III) The second sub-question examines the psychological dimension: How do individuals' attitudes regarding trust in space-based technologies influence their perceptions of personal data protection in space?

¹² Hoofnagle, C. J., van der Sloot, B., & Zuiderveen Borgesius, F. (2019). The European Union general data protection regulation: What it is and what it means. *Information & Communications Technology Law*, 28(1), 65–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600834.2019.1573501>.

¹³ Zoltick, M. M., and Colgate J. L. (2019). *The application of data protection laws in (outer) space*, 6–11.

¹⁴ Kastlová, H. (2024, April 17). Report on extraterritorial enforcement of GDPR. European Data Protection Board.

¹⁵ Mishova, A. (2024, October 28). *Global data protection regulation: How GDPR sets the international standard*. GDPR Local. <https://gdprlocal.com/global-data-protection-regulation-how-gdpr-sets-the-international-standard/>.

¹⁶ Pickens, J. (2005). Attitudes and perceptions. In N. Borkowski (Ed.), *Organizational behavior in health care* (pp. 43–75). Jones & Bartlett Publishers.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Two primary gaps can be identified in the literature concerning relevant legal and psychological scholarship. First, the unprecedented applicability of the GDPR to space-based observation satellites. Second, the limited integration of relevant psychological insights, particularly those concerning trust attitudes and privacy perceptions, within legal analyses of space-based personal data collection.

3.1. *The Limits of the GDPR applied to Outer Space*

3.1.1. *The GDPR*

The GDPR,¹⁷ adopted by the European Union (EU) in 2016 and enforced on May 25, 2018, represents one of the most significant advancements in personal data policy.¹⁸ The GDPR is specifically aimed at safeguarding the personal data and privacy rights of individuals within the EU and the European Economic Area (EEA) and extends its scope beyond EU territory by requiring non-EU entities processing the personal data of individuals in the Union to comply.¹⁹ The regulation inter alia establishes a detailed, comprehensive framework of rules on specifically the collection, processing, and storing of data, applying to companies, governments, and organizations.²⁰

3.1.2. *Extraterritorial Scope*

While no legal framework explicitly governs space-based data collection, the GDPR is frequently referenced for this in legal and academic discussions due to its broad extraterritorial scope.²¹ The relevance stems largely from Article 3(2), which extends the regulation's applicability to data controllers and processors not established in the EU if they process personal data of individuals located within the EU.²² In the context of space-based technologies, this may extend to satellite systems operated from outside the EU that collect personal data pertaining to EU citizens.

3.1.3. *Application to Outer Space*

Existing literature largely agrees that the GDPR potentially extends to personal data at space-based satellites. However, its applicability has neither been explicitly articulated within current regulatory texts nor applied in practice.²³ Moreover, given that satellites operate in outer space, their characteristics differ fundamentally from terrestrial data processing to which the GDPR typically applies. Martin Zoltick and Jenny Colgate highlight the pressing need for the development of an international treaty or an updated regulatory framework that delineates jurisdictional authority over actors involved in

¹⁷ The GDPR replaced the 1995 Data Protection Directive (Directive 95/46/EC).

¹⁸ Hoofnagle, C. J., van der Sloot, B., & Zuiderveen Borgesius, F. (2019). The European Union general data protection regulation: What it is and what it means. *Information & Communications Technology Law*, 28(1), 65–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600834.2019.1573501>.

¹⁹ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ Bu-Pasha, S., & Kuusniemi, H. (2021). Data protection and space: What challenges will the General Data Protection Regulation face when dealing with space-based data? *Journal of Data Protection & Privacy*, 4(1), 52–58. https://osuva.uwasa.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/12271/Osuva_Bu-Pasha_Kuusniemi_2021.pdf.

²² Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

²³ Bu-Pasha, S., & Kuusniemi, H. (2021). Data protection and space: What challenges will the General Data Protection Regulation face when dealing with space-based data? *Journal of Data Protection & Privacy*, 4(1), 52–58. https://osuva.uwasa.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/12271/Osuva_Bu-Pasha_Kuusniemi_2021.pdf.

the collection of personal data beyond national territories, such as in outer space.²⁴ Such a framework would be essential to determine which legal entity, whether national, regional, or international, has the right to govern, investigate, or adjudicate activities involving personal data collection in space.²⁵

In contrast to the aforementioned authors, Laura Keogh highlights that the GDPR remains the primary data protection framework within the EU.²⁶ She emphasises that it should continue to be regarded as the most relevant personal data protection framework in the context of the evolving space sector.²⁷ Her perspectives align with the broader scholarly view that prioritises the need for clearer interpretations and extensions of the GDPR's existing provisions to space-related activities, rather than advocating for the creation of entirely new legal frameworks.²⁸

Thus, scholars generally maintain that the GDPR is already applicable to space-related data processing, although its application in this context remains largely untested in practice. However, questions remain regarding the allocation of jurisdiction over actors involved in personal data processing beyond national territories. Accordingly, this research conducts a holistic analysis of how the existing regulatory framework may operate in relation to space-based technologies.

3.2. *Types of Satellites Considered*

Roopashree Sharma explains that there are different types of satellites involved in data processing or collecting.²⁹ Among these are observation, communication, and navigation satellites. These categories differ in function and data handling capacity.³⁰ While examining the full spectrum of satellite types could be valuable, this article specifically focuses on observation satellites. This decision is grounded in technical relevance: observation satellites are distinct in that they typically store personal data for prolonged durations, whereas other types either transmit it in real time or are not intended to retain it.³¹

Riccardo Patriarca et al. argue that the extended data retention associated with observation satellites increases the risk of personal data breaches.³² This concern is grounded in the satellite's capacity to store sensitive information related to individuals. Examples of sensitive data concerning observation satellites include high-resolution imagery, as well as other forms of Earth observation data that can capture identifiable human activity.³³

3.3. *Psychological Perspectives: Trust Attitudes and Perceptions*

The psychological dimension of this explores individuals' trust and perceptions of space-based technologies and their attitudes regarding the protection of their personal data. Psychological lenses concerning these specific matters remain largely underexplored in relation to space-based personal data collection. To address this gap, this section engages with established psychological research.

²⁴ Zoltick, M. M., and Colgate J. L. (2019). *The application of data protection laws in (outer) space*, 6–11.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Keogh, L. (2023). EU data protection considerations for the space sector. In P. J. Blount & M.

Hofmann (Eds.), *Space law in a networked world* (pp. 230–255). Brill. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004527270_011.

²⁷ Ibid, p. 251.

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Sharma, R. (2024, September 4). *Types of satellites and their applications*. Jagran Josh.

<https://www.jagranjosh.com/general-knowledge/types-of-satellites-and-their-applications-1725441333-1>.

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Ibid.

³² Patriarca, R., Costantino, F., & Di Gravio, G. (2019). Risk, safety, reliability and satellites: Chronicles of a fragmented research field. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 6(3), 201–211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jssse.2019.08.002>.

³³ Ibid.

Although research on trust attitudes in the context of space observation satellites remains scarce, there is a study by McAmis et al. that examines how American citizens perceive the capabilities and implications of commercial satellite imagery.³⁴ Through interview data, participants express discomfort or a lack of understanding regarding observatory satellite data practices, especially in light of privacy.³⁵ Moreover, participants highlight the importance of regulation in this domain.³⁶ The authors note that these perceptions are particularly relevant given the increasing accuracy of satellite imagery.³⁷

A key takeaway from the study is the widespread concerns among citizens regarding observation satellites, as well as the stressed importance of incorporating constructs such as trust and perceived risk into conceptualisations of regulatory frameworks.³⁸ However, it is important to note that this research was conducted solely in the United States. Further research across diverse contexts is needed to enhance the generalisability of these findings and to extend insights to European citizens. On the other hand, given the global nature of satellite observation technologies, these findings can hold tentative relevance for European citizens as well.

To continue, a meta-analysis by Leschanowsky et al. examines how individuals perceive privacy, security, and trust in artificial intelligence (AI) systems. These include, for example, chatbots and voice assistants.³⁹ The study reveals that numerous individuals express concern regarding the collection, storage, and potential misuse of their personal data.⁴⁰ Specifically, users' concerns regarding privacy and potential data misuse play a critical role in shaping their trust, particularly in environments where personal data is handled by systems that are technologically complex or lack transparency.⁴¹

There are notable parallels regarding trust, privacy, and perceived data security in the context of space-based data collection and AI mechanisms. Namely, similar to satellite technologies, AI systems employ complex and technical methods for collecting data.⁴² Consequently, existing literature suggests that both technologies generate comparable public concerns related to trust, surveillance, and feelings of diminished control.⁴³ Therefore, the low levels of perceived trust, privacy, and data security observed in other technological domains appear similarly applicable to space-based systems, including observation satellites.⁴⁴ This is further reinforced by the growing integration of AI in space-based observation satellites, which increasingly rely on AI to process, analyse, and interpret the vast amounts of data they collect.⁴⁵ In fact, observation satellites and AI are becoming increasingly interdependent, with AI

³⁴ McAmis, R., Sim, M., Bennett, M., & Kohno, T. (2024). Over fences and into yards: Privacy Threats and concerns of commercial satellites. *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2024(1), 379–396. <https://doi.org/10.56553/popets-2024-0022>.

³⁵ Ibid, 384–385

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Ibid, 389–390

³⁹ Leschanowsky, A., Rech, S., Popp, B., & Bäckström, T. (2024). Evaluating privacy, security, and trust perceptions in conversational AI: A systematic review. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 159(2), Article 108344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2024.108344>.

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ Ibid, 18.

⁴² Zuboff, S. (2019). *The age of surveillance capitalism: The fight for a human future at the new frontier of power*. PublicAffairs.

⁴³ Ibid; Lyons, S. (2023). Satellite surveillance and the orbital unconscious. *New Media & Society*, 27(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448231187352>.

⁴⁴ Zuboff, S. (2019). *The age of surveillance capitalism: The fight for a human future at the new frontier of power*. PublicAffairs.

⁴⁵ Lachner, C., Mann, Z. Á., & Dustdar, S. (2021). Towards understanding the adaptation space of AI-assisted data protection for video analytics at the edge. In *Proceedings of the 2021 IEEE 41st International Conference on*

functioning as an essential component of satellite operations, making it difficult to consider the two in isolation from one another.⁴⁶

In addition to this, the lack of public trust, specifically in observation satellites, is suggested by broader distrust in satellite technologies and outer space systems in general.⁴⁷ Since observation satellites are central to personal data collection, the general distrust in satellite technologies directly applies to them. Literature highlights that this distrust stems from a fundamental lack of transparency and the inability of current legal frameworks to keep pace with the autonomous and large-scale nature of surveillance, particularly when facilitated by complex, AI-driven technologies in space.⁴⁸

4. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

4.1. *Legal Positivism and Its Modern Application*

The legal dimension of this study is grounded in the theory of legal positivism, which conceives that the validity of law stems from legislation, formal procedures, and court decisions, rather than satisfying politics or social configurations.⁴⁹ Consequently, a legal positivist perspective is appropriate for examining the GDPR, which represents a codified, rules-based approach to data protection governance. While classical legal positivism avoids normative assessments, this article additionally engages with a modern conceptualization of legal positivism that, in addition, examines normative considerations as integral to the interpretation and practical application of legal provisions.⁵⁰ This approach facilitates a more nuanced analysis.⁵¹

4.2. *The Sparrow Framework*

Furthermore, this article adopts Malcolm Sparrow's safety-management framework to support the exploration of the overarching research question by examining the balance between legal and psychological dimensions. Sparrow's conceptualisation visualises the relationship between legal and harmful phenomena through a Venn diagram.⁵² Essentially, the left side of the model represents matters that are addressed through existing legal mechanisms and enforcement structures. In contrast, the right side pertains to risks that are not formally governed by law but nonetheless pose significant harm to

Distributed Computing Systems Workshops (ICDCSW) (pp. 7–12). IEEE.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDCSW53096.2021.00009>.

⁴⁶ Ghiglione, M., & Serra, V. (2022). Opportunities and challenges of AI on satellite processing units. In *Proceedings of the 19th ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers (CF '22)* (221–224). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3528416.3530985>; Yazici, T., Martin, A.-S., Wood, S., Kucher, L., Almenar, R., Zielinski, L. Y., Wedenig, S.-M., & Tricco, G. (2025). *Balancing innovation and responsibility: International recommendations for AI regulation in space*. *Acta Astronautica*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2025.04.063>.

⁴⁷ McKenna, A. T., Gaudion, A. C., & Evans, J. L. (2020). The role of satellites and smart devices: Data surprises and security, privacy, and regulatory challenges. *University of Pennsylvania Journal of International Law*, 42(2), 289–342.

⁴⁸ Gerlich, M. (2024). Public anxieties about AI: Implications for corporate strategy and societal impact. *Administrative Sciences*, 14(11), 288. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci14110288>.

⁴⁹ Himma, K. E. (2019). Legal positivism. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter 2019 Edition). Stanford University. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2019/entries/legal-positivism/>.

⁵⁰ Simma, B., & Paulus, A. L. (1999). The responsibility of individuals for human rights abuses in internal conflicts: A positivist view. *American Journal of International Law*, 93(2), 302–316. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2997991>

⁵¹ Ibid.

⁵² While the Venn diagram is discussed in *The Character of Harms*, the actual visual representation does not appear in the book itself but is included in a presentation Sparrow gave at the Twelfth Annual Symposium of the Performance and Planning Exchange on May 27, 2008. The presentation is available at: http://www.ppx.ca/download/symposiums/2008/keynote/2008_pp_Sparrow_e.pdf.

society.⁵³ The core idea of this model is to visualise how certain harms, though argued to lie outside the legal framework, may still warrant regulatory attention if they fall within the scope of the right side.⁵⁴ In doing so, the model challenges the traditional line between what is legally regulated and what is socially or ethically concerning.

Figure 1 (Sparrow,

2008)

The closely associated theories developed by Malcolm Sparrow are often described as bridging the gap between legal governance and the social dimension of harm prevention.⁵⁵ When Sparrow's model is applied to the analysis presented later in this article, it serves as an analytical tool to contextualise the findings, directly pertaining to the overarching research question. Consequently, when falling in the right category, it is imperative that regulatory authorities, in each national context, do not confine their approach solely to existing legal frameworks but also consider broader forms of oversight governance where necessary.⁵⁶

5. METHODOLOGY

This article employs a multi-methodological approach, combining legal doctrinal analysis with psychological theoretical research and qualitative empirical inquiry.⁵⁷ To answer the first sub-research question, a doctrinal analysis is conducted, serving as the central methodological component of this study. It specifically focuses on the extraterritorial scope of Article 3 of the GDPR and is structured according to the IRAC method. This method provides a systematic framework for identifying the legal issue, stating the relevant rule, applying it to the specific context, and formulating a conclusion.⁵⁸

⁵³ Sparrow, M. K. (2008). *The character of harms: Operational challenges in control*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511753862>.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Engells, T. E. (2010, May). The character of harms: Operational challenges in control. *Security Management*. <https://www.asisonline.org/security-management-magazine/articles/2010/05/the-character-of-harms-operational-challenges-in-control/>.

⁵⁶ Sparrow, M. K. (2008). *The character of harms: Operational challenges in control*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511753862>.

⁵⁷ Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2019). *Research methods for business students* (8th ed.). Pearson Education.

⁵⁸ Neumann, R. K., Jr., & Tiscione, K. K. (2009). *Legal reasoning and legal writing* (7th ed.). Wolters Kluwer Law & Business.

The doctrinal analysis systematically researches the content of Article 3 of the GDPR, together with other relevant legal provisions and accompanying recitals.⁵⁹ Given the highly contemporary nature of satellite-based data processing, relevant case law remains limited. As a result, this study additionally relies on academic commentary, scholarly literature, and other soft law tools to supplement the gaps that exist within the currently available materials.

Moreover, the analysis examines *the Google Spain case*.⁶⁰ This ruling substantially influenced contemporary interpretations of the GDPR's extraterritorial scope. Particularly in the context of space-based personal data processing, this case's relevance lies in comparable challenges related to jurisdiction and enforceability.

Furthermore, the analysis considers interpretative guidance issued by influential bodies, including the European Data Protection Board (EDPB), which is a crucial institution for interpreting and overseeing the implementation of EU data protection law. The integration of all the elements aforementioned establishes the foundation for addressing the legal dimension of this analysis.

Following this, the Sparrow model is applied to the findings from the prior sections. This helps reveal that the balance between legal applicability and socio-psychological perceptions is either reinforced or undermined by the latter. Thus, this section synthesises and weighs all findings against each other, providing an integrated reflection that suggests future recommendations. It includes recommendations for legal interpretation, as well as alternative measures to be taken when the applicability of the GDPR to space proves insufficient.

Lastly, this study employs semi-structured interviews as a methodological tool to gather more in-depth insights from different experts. Qualitative methods, such as interviews, are valuable for capturing nuanced perceptions, especially in evolving and technically complicated fields.⁶¹ Therefore, to gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter, four interviews were conducted with diverse specialists.

Each of the four interviewees brings a distinct and complementary perspective to the topic at hand. Monique Verdier, the Deputy Chair of Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens (AP), being the Dutch Data Protection Authority (DPA), offers insights from a regulatory and oversight standpoint. Barbara Kathmann, Member of the Dutch Parliament and a member of the Parliamentary Committee on Digital Affairs, provides a legislative and policy-oriented view. Bart Schermer, Professor of Privacy and Cybercrime at Leiden University, brings academic and theoretical expertise. Lastly, Michiel Steltman, former Director of the Dutch Digital Infrastructure Foundation (DINL), adds a perspective grounded in the practical realities of digital infrastructure and technological implementation. Only Dutch experts were interviewed. Nevertheless, all four interviewees may be considered representative of broader EU perspectives, given

⁵⁹ Bhagyamma, G. (2023). *A comparative analysis of doctrinal and non-doctrinal legal research*. *ILE Journal of Governance and Policy Review*, 1(1), p.88.

⁶⁰ Case C-131/12, *Google Spain SL and Google Inc. v. Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (AEPD) and Mario Costeja González*, 2014 ECLI:EU:C:2014:317

⁶¹ Luger, E., & Sellen, A. (2016). "Like having a really bad PA": The gulf between user expectation and experience of conversational agents. In *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 5286–5297). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2858036.2858288>; Cowan, B. R., Pantidi, N., Coyle, D., Morrissey, K., Clarke, P., Al-Shehri, S., Earley, D., & Bandeira, N. (2017). "What can I help you with?": Infrequent users' experiences of intelligent personal assistants. *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction with Mobile Devices and Services (MobileHCI'17 '17)*, Article 43, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3098279.3098539>; Binns, R., Veale, M., Van Kleek, M., & Shadbolt, N. (2018). "It's reducing a human being to a percentage": Perceptions of justice in algorithmic decisions. *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '18)*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3173574.3173951>.

their professional engagement within the Dutch regulatory and legal landscape, which is embedded in the EU framework.

6. DOCTRINAL ANALYSIS

6.1. Framing the Legal Issue

The legal issue is whether Article 3 of the GDPR applies to personal data collected by space-based Earth-observation satellites operated by entities within its jurisdiction. It examines whether personal data breaches involving the transmission or leakage of such data to third parties fall within the extraterritorial scope of the Regulation.

To further contextualise potential risks, the interviewees offer complementary insights. Michiel Steltman emphasises that when personal data falls into the wrong hands, it can give rise to unforeseen risks.⁶² Bart Schermer adds that the rise of AI fundamentally shifts the privacy landscape, as even anonymised data may be re-identified and linked back to individuals.⁶³ Monique Verdier underscores the severity of misuse by referencing real-world consequences, including identity fraud, and, in extreme cases, suicides resulting from reputational damage.⁶⁴ Such harms may stem from the misuse of personal data types, including geolocation patterns or behavioural profiles derived from satellite imagery, particularly when these are enhanced through AI-driven analysis and used to infer identity, monitor movement, or draw sensitive conclusions about individuals. These potential harms underscore the need to examine whether, and to what extent, the GDPR covers such risks.

6.2. Examining Article 3 GDPR: Territorial Scope

The following sections examine the relevant legal provisions and definitions of the GDPR articles, relevant case law, interpretative guidance from the EDPB, and an analysis of the relevant recitals. As a directly applicable EU regulation, the GDPR takes precedence over conflicting national laws, thereby holding a prominent position within the European legal order as a binding instrument of primary legislation.⁶⁵ In general, Article 3 outlines the geographic and jurisdictional conditions under which the GDPR is applicable. Article 3(3) is not addressed in this analysis, as the primary relevance for the discussion lies in provisions 3(1) and 3(2).

6.2.1. Article 3(1): Establishment in the Union

Article 3(1) GDPR states: “The regulation applies to the processing of personal data in the context of the activities of an establishment of a controller or a processor in the Union, regardless of whether the processing takes place in the Union or not.”⁶⁶ The provision thus formulates that entities within the EU remain subject to GDPR obligations. This applies even when their data processing activities are carried out beyond EU territory, regulating its applicability extraterritorially.⁶⁷

⁶² Author interview with Michiel Steltman (Former Director of the Dutch Digital Infrastructure Foundation), 19 May 2025.

⁶³ Author interview with Bart Schermer (Privacy and Cybercrime Professor at Leiden University), 19 May 2025.

⁶⁴ Author interview with Monique Verdier (Deputy Chair Dutch DPA), 2 June 2025.

⁶⁵ Consolidated Version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union., 2012 O.J. C (326)/47. Art. 288.

⁶⁶ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

⁶⁷ Gil González, E., & de Hert, P. (2019). Understanding the legal provisions that allow processing and profiling of personal data - An analysis of GDPR provisions and principles. *ERA Forum*, 19(4), 597–621. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12027-018-0546-z>.

6.2.2. Article 3(2): Targeting or Monitoring in the Union

Article 3(2) GDPR broadens the territorial scope. It states: “This Regulation applies to the processing of personal data of data subjects who are in the Union by a controller or processor not established in the Union, where the processing activities are related to: (a) the offering of goods or services, irrespective of whether a payment of the data subject is required, to such data subjects in the Union; or (b) the monitoring of their behaviour as far as their behaviour takes place within the Union.⁶⁸” In other words, this provision prioritises the impact on EU data subjects, preventing parties from evading its protections based on location.⁶⁹

6.2.3. Article 4: Definitions

Article 4 of the GDPR provides key terminological clarifications to gain insight into definitions within these provisions. The most relevant definitions for assessing the applicability to space-based observation satellites are Article 4(1), 4(7), and 4(8). Article 4(1) defines *personal data*. It states: “personal data means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.⁷⁰”

Furthermore, Article 4(7) defines a *controller*: “the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law.” Lastly, Article 4(8) defines a *processor*: “a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller.” As clarified in Article 29 Working Party Opinion 3,⁷¹ determining whether an entity qualifies as a controller or processor under EU data protection law is essential for assessing the applicability of the GDPR. These definitions further enable the GDPR to be applied, insofar as the processing involves personal data that can be linked to individuals located within the EU.⁷² While the articles and definitions offer foundational insights, it remains essential to consult supplementary sources to develop a more comprehensive understanding.

6.2.4. Google Spain Case

The case *Google Spain SL and Google Inc. v. Agencia Española de Protección de Datos* is a key judgment that offers valuable insights into the territorial scope of the GDPR that can be relevant for assessing its applicability to space-based satellites.⁷³ The case is about Mr Costeja González, who sought the removal of sensitive personal information linked to his name from Google’s search results. Although Google’s headquarters were located in the United States, the Court held that the company was still subject

⁶⁸ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

⁶⁹ Höglund, W. (2018). *The extraterritorial reach of the GDPR: Exporting data protection law*. Umeå University Publications.

⁷⁰ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

⁷¹ Refers to EU advisory body that issued influential guidance on data protection prior to the GDPR, only cited in this article where no updated interpretation exists.

⁷² Mondschein, C. F., & Monda, C. (2018). *The EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in a research context* (Chapter 5). In P. Kubben, M. Dumontier, & A. Dekker (Eds.), *Fundamentals of clinical data science*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99771-8_5.

⁷³ Case C-131/12, *Google Spain SL and Google Inc. v. Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (AEPD) and Mario Costeja González*, 2014 ECLI:EU:C:2014:317.

to EU data protection law and required it to remove the information.⁷⁴ The CJEU had to decide on the interpretation of “establishment” in Article 3(1).⁷⁵ According to them, the term “establishment” must be interpreted broadly, given that entities based outside the EU can still fall under the GDPR’s territorial scope if they direct their activities toward EU individuals.⁷⁶

In contrast, in AG Niilo Jääskinen’s 2013 Opinion, he highlighted the importance of a narrow interpretation of the term “establishment”⁷⁷. He argued that the mere presence of a subsidiary within the EU does not suffice to bring a non-EU company, such as Google Inc., within the territorial scope of EU data protection law.⁷⁸ Therefore, he articulated a limitation on the broad interpretation of the extraterritorial scope of the GDPR, which gained considerable support. Although the CJEU ruled differently on the case, AG Jääskinen’s 2013 Opinion remains doctrinally interesting. While not legally binding, AG Opinions carry persuasive authority and are often cited for their detailed legal reasoning and interpretative frameworks.⁷⁹ Jääskinen’s insistence on a narrow reading of “establishment” underscores potential limits on the GDPR’s extraterritorial scope.

6.2.5. EDPB’s Guidelines 3/2018

The EDPB issues non-binding soft law recommendations but holds significant interpretative authority. The EDPB Guidelines 3/2018 describe when the GDPR applies outside the EU, in light of Article 3(1) and 3(2).⁸⁰ In essence, it emphasises that the applicability of the GDPR is primarily determined by the location and legal rights of the data subject.

The EDPB elaborates that “establishment” in Article 3(1) is to be interpreted in a broad sense.⁸¹ They emphasise that the determining factor for GDPR applicability is the existence of operational links, rather than the physical location of processing infrastructure. They state: “The decisive factor is whether the processing is carried out in the context of the activities of the EU establishment.”⁸² This is particularly relevant given that once the criterion for “establishment” is fulfilled, a controller or processor must respect data subject rights as per the articles of the GDPR.

Regarding Article 3(2), the EDPB affirms that the targeting criterion applies when a non-EU entity monitors the behaviour of individuals in the EU.⁸³ The deciding factor is the data subject’s presence in the EU at the time of processing, irrespective of nationality. This furthermore ensures that data subjects in the EU are protected from invasive data practices, even when carried out by entities based outside the EU.⁸⁴

6.2.6. Recital 15: Technology Neutrality

Recital 15 offers additional interpretative insight into the scope and application of the relevant provisions, particularly by emphasising the notion of technology neutrality. Recital 15(1) states: “In order to prevent

⁷⁴ Ibid.

⁷⁵ Ibid.

⁷⁶ Ibid; Frantziou, E. (2014). Further developments in the right to be forgotten: The European Court of Justice's judgment in Case C-131/12, *Google Spain, SL, Google Inc. v Agencia*.

Española de Protección de Datos. *Human Rights Law Review*, 14(4), 761–777. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hrlr/ngu033>.

⁷⁷ Jääskinen, N. (2013). Opinion of Advocate General Jääskinen, *Google Spain SL and Google Inc. v Agencia Española de Protección de Datos*, Case C-131/12, ECLI:EU:C:2014:317.

⁷⁸ Ibid, para 63.

⁷⁹ Mañko, R. (2019). *Role of Advocates General at the CJEU* (EPRS Briefing PE 642.237). European Parliamentary Research Service. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI\(2019\)642237](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI(2019)642237).

⁸⁰ EDPB, 2018.

⁸¹ EDPB, 2018, p. 5.

⁸² EDPB, 2018, p. 8.

⁸³ EDPB, 2018, pp.13-15.

⁸⁴ EDPB, 2018.

creating a serious risk of circumvention, the protection of natural persons should be technologically neutral and should not depend on the techniques used”⁸⁵. Thus, the type of technology is secondary to the concern of ensuring the protection of individuals’ personal data. The focus lies on the impact on the data subject, rather than the specific tools or systems through which the processing occurs.⁸⁶

6.3. *Assessing the Applicability*

An initial examination of the content of Articles 3(1) and 3(2) suggests that the GDPR may extend to space-based satellite-derived personal data concerning identifiable individuals within the EU. This is irrespective of the satellite’s physical location in outer space. However, additional analysis is required to determine the full extent of this applicability.

When interpreted in the context of space-based observation satellites, the definitions set out in Articles 4(1), 4(7), and 4(8) can be applied to collected personal data. For example, geolocation patterns or behavioural profiles generated through satellite imagery, especially when enhanced by AI technologies, may fall within the scope of “personal data” under Article 4(1), insofar as they relate to an identified or identifiable natural person. Furthermore, “controllers,” as defined in Article 4(7) of the GDPR, may include satellite operators that determine the purposes and means of processing satellite-derived personal data, such as Maxar Technologies or Airbus Defence and Space. “Processors,” as defined in Article 4(8), can refer to third parties, certain actors on Earth or in space that handle the data on behalf of the controller. These may include image analytics firms or government contractors such as Planet Labs PBC or Maxar Intelligence.⁸⁷

The examined case law confirms that the notion of extraterritoriality should be interpreted broadly, potentially allowing for its application to space-based satellites. However, such an extension may remain somewhat ambiguous. This uncertainty is underscored by AG Jääskinen’s 2013 Opinion, in which he advocated for a narrower interpretation of the territorial scope. If a limitation on the interpretation of establishment is already suggested by AG Jääskinen in the terrestrial context, extending the concept to outer space appears even less self-evident. As previously noted, although this opinion lacks binding legal force, it carries significant academic weight and contributes to the interpretative discourse on the scope of the GDPR.

Furthermore, given that the EDPB emphasises that “monitoring” includes observation beyond online tracking, it potentially covers Earth observation technologies. Thus, the Guidelines appear to affirm that the GDPR applies extraterritorially to observation satellites where data subjects are in the EU, or the processing is linked to an EU-based individual. Additionally, the notion of technological neutrality per Recital 15 of the GDPR implies that space-based technologies should also fall within the regulation’s scope; the focus lies on the protection of personal data, irrespective of the means or tools used to process, including space-based observation satellites.⁸⁸

Lastly, it is noteworthy that neither the text of the GDPR nor its recitals makes any explicit reference to satellites or outer space.⁸⁹ This omission makes it difficult to assert with certainty that the GDPR applies to space-based contexts. Especially, as stated in the literature review, given that satellites operate in outer

⁸⁵ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

⁸⁶ Ibid.

⁸⁷ FlyPix AI. (2025, April 12). Leading satellite image processing companies delivering precision. <https://flypix.ai>

⁸⁸ Regulation 679/2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, 2016 O.J. (L 119) 1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

⁸⁹ Ibid.

space, their characteristics differ fundamentally from terrestrial data processing. As a result, one can argue that a degree of ambiguity remains, and further clarification from relevant interpretative bodies is needed to determine whether the GDPR may be legitimately applied.

Thus, from a legal positivistic perspective, the text and purpose of the GDPR, especially Articles 3(1), 3(2), 4(1), 4(7) and 4(8), supported by relevant case law, EDPS Guidelines, and Recital 15, suggest that its territorial scope could extend to space-based personal data in observation satellites from EU individuals or people that are in the EU. However, this interpretation is not without legal uncertainty. The absence of explicit references in any of the material to satellites or outer space, coupled with competing views from AG Jääskinen's opinion and other scholars, indicates that such an extension is plausible but currently constitutes a far-reaching interpretation. Moreover, this interpretation is yet to be applied in practice, further contributing to its legal uncertainty. Ultimately, this article contends that further legal clarification, particularly from authoritative bodies such as the EDPB, is essential to solidify the GDPR's applicability to space-based observation satellites.

However, from a normative perspective, considering the concerns surrounding public distrust and fear highlighted in the psychological sections, as well as the emphasis in Recital 15 on ensuring broad and technologically neutral protection, this article argues that the GDPR ought to be interpreted as extending to space-based observation satellites. That is furthermore because, as prior sections state, for European citizens, the GDPR constitutes the most comprehensive privacy framework currently in place, and the importance of safeguarding against associated risks is considerable.

7. SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL DIMENSION

The doctrinal analysis reveals that the GDPR does not provide undeniable certainty when it comes to the protection of individuals' personal data in the context of outer-space observation satellites. Consequently, the interest of the socio-psychological dimension increases. There remains an open issue as to whether a meaningful balance exists between legal protection and societal concern. However, the literature review of this article demonstrates that individuals express significant discomfort and concerns regarding space-based satellite surveillance and personal data misuse. The interview data complement these findings. For instance, Monique Verdier highlights the overwhelming public reaction to the DPA's call to object to META's use of personal data for AI training, indicating widespread unease and a lack of clarity.⁹⁰ Interestingly, Barbara Kathmann also notes this as an example of a growing unease in public perception.⁹¹ Bart Schermer describes how he sees that individuals often accept tracking, not out of genuine consent but due to limited alternatives, reinforcing a sense of coercion.⁹² In conclusion, there is a clear imbalance: while public concern is high, the law itself remains inadequate.

8. INTEGRATING DIMENSIONS: LEGAL GAPS AND PERCEIVED HARM

8.1. *A Disconnect Between Law and Attitudes*

The disparity between the legal reality and public concern underscores the urgent need for robust regulatory frameworks to ensure adequate protection of personal data in outer space. The following sections aim to explore ways to restore balance between the two dimensions, while emphasizing that legal clarification is, first and foremost, desirable. When returning to the core of why public trust is low and why regulatory safeguards are necessary, the underlying concern lies in the concepts of potential harm.

⁹⁰ Author interview with Monique Verdier (Deputy Chair Dutch DPA), 2 June 2025.

⁹¹ Author interview with Barbara Kathmann (Member of the Dutch Parliament for PVDA/GroenLinks and Member of the Parliamentary Committee on Digital Affairs), 16 June 2025.

⁹² Author interview with Bart Schermer (Privacy and Cybercrime Professor at Leiden University), 19 May 2025.

Legal frameworks aim to regulate and prevent harm, whilst simultaneously, low perceptions of trust often circulate potential harm. Accordingly, the following sections investigate whether an alternative approach to safeguarding against such risks may be warranted. To that end, this study applies the Sparrow diagram to identify which entities, besides GDPR-regulated actors, bear responsibility for mitigating risk and harm, and to reframe the legal and psychological findings in a more integrated perspective. This synthesis ultimately supports the formulation of a conclusion to the overarching research question.

8.2. *Applying the Malcolm Sparrow Framework*

This article employs Malcolm Sparrow's diagram and accompanying theoretical framework as an evaluative perspective to further synthesise the legal and psychological dimensions of the research.⁹³ This allows for an analysis that extends beyond the boundaries of legally governed harm to consider broader societal risks. This study argues that Sparrow's dual perspective is particularly relevant to space-based observation satellites, given their distinctive regulatory challenges and psychological characteristics that do not easily align with traditional legal boundaries. As stated before, the doctrinal analysis of Article 3 of the GDPR demonstrates that while the regulation may extend extraterritorially, its application to satellite-based data collection remains legally uncertain. When applied, personal data in space may lie at the margins, or even outside, the formal legal domain, being the left side of Sparrow's diagram.⁹⁴ However, the risks evidently reside within the sphere of societal harm and are thereby situated on the right side. Consequently, even if the protection of personal data regarding observation satellites does not fall within the domain of established legal regulation, it becomes all the more essential to address the risks, situated on the right side. Precisely because these risks lie beyond the reach of existing legal frameworks, they may warrant even greater regulatory or oversight attention.⁹⁵

Furthermore, Sparrow emphasises the critical role of national supervisory authorities, particularly in addressing risks that fall within the right sphere.⁹⁶ Moreover, he explains that even if these stakeholders are not always legally obligated, they nonetheless carry ethical and practical responsibilities in responding to the risks that emerge. A complementary illustration of this idea is that the Deputy Chair of the Dutch DPA elaborates that she thinks that supervisory bodies have the essential responsibility to not only monitor adherence to certain rules but also to identify and respond to evolving societal risk, especially in areas where legal frameworks may still be underdeveloped.⁹⁷ This statement aligns with the position advanced by Aute Kasdorp, who builds upon Sparrow's framework and argues that, when risks fall within the right side of Sparrow's model, it is ultimately up to the supervisory authority to determine the role it wishes to assume in response.⁹⁸ This indicates that it may not only be desirable in cases of risk, but foremost legally permissible for authoritative bodies to apply their regulatory mandates to other emerging risks.

To situate the foregoing within an exhaustive context, in light of ambiguity regarding the GDPR's applicability, risks to personal data fall inarguably on the right side of Sparrow's model; that is, outside the domain of formal legal regulation. This, in turn, necessitates regulatory attention. Accordingly, it underscores the significance of supervision beyond strictly defined responsibilities laid down in the

⁹³ Sparrow, M. K. (2008). *The character of harms: Operational challenges in control*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511753862>.

⁹⁴ Sparrow, M. K. (2008, May 27). *The character of harms: Operational challenges in control* [Keynote presentation]. Twelfth Annual Symposium of the Performance and Planning Exchange, Ottawa, Canada. http://www.ppx.ca/download/symposiums/2008/keynote/2008_pp_Sparrow_e.pdf.

⁹⁵ Ibid.

⁹⁶ Ibid.

⁹⁷ Author interview with Monique Verdier (Deputy Chair Dutch DPA), 2 June 2025.

⁹⁸ Kasdorp, E.-A. (2022). *Between Scylla and Charybdis: Regulators' supervisory practice in the face of harmful but legal regulatee conduct* [Doctoral dissertation, Erasmus University Rotterdam]. 51–62. <https://reader.ogc.nl/fceec8e51-657d-4280-b033-a42964c2ef9b.epub/>.

GDPR, especially for national supervisory authorities entrusted with wider regulatory and oversight responsibilities.

9. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE TRAJECTORY

Trust in the GDPR as a legal framework in itself is a distinct and valuable topic, but one that would broaden the scope of this article beyond its intended focus. Nevertheless, it remains closely connected to the issues discussed above. Combining these insights may offer valuable perspectives for future research.

In conclusion, this article demonstrates that the protection of personal data in the context of outer space observation satellites holds substantial societal relevance and warrants serious regulatory attention. To explore this theme, the study employs a multi-methodological approach that integrates legal doctrinal analysis, psychological theoretical research, and qualitative empirical inquiry with experts. Its interdisciplinary framework highlights how the potential applicability of Article 3 of the GDPR to space-based observation satellites intersects with public trust perceptions among European citizens, thereby generating a novel and integrative insight not previously explored.

The legal analysis reveals that the text and intent of the GDPR suggest potential applicability to the personal data collected by these satellites. However, the distinctive legal context of outer space, the absence of explicit references to space-based technologies, and the fact that this interpretation has not yet been tested in practice may give rise to certain jurisdictional and interpretative ambiguities. Thus, while plausible, the application of Article 3 of the GDPR to personal data in the context of space-based observation satellites would benefit from further legal clarification by authoritative legal bodies. From a normative perspective, this article argues that outer-space observation satellites should fall under the scope of the GDPR, especially in light of the risks and the regulation's regulatory influence. From a psychological perspective, public perceptions reflect low levels of trust in space-based satellite technologies and the protection of personal data, influenced by concerns over surveillance and a lack of transparency. Therefore, the importance of robust legal safeguards increases.

The application of the Sparrow framework facilitates further integration of the legal and psychological dimensions. It highlights that even if the risks associated with personal data regarding observation satellites fall outside the scope of current legal frameworks, they still warrant regulatory attention. This emphasises supervisory authorities as crucial actors in addressing these societal harms, even in legally uncertain domains. The interdisciplinary character of this study is essential for creating an exhaustive overview, as the societal impact of personal data in space-based observation satellites extends beyond what legal frameworks alone can sufficiently capture.

As highlighted at the outset of this study, personal data breaches are not only on the rise, they are escalating at a global scale. The risks carry serious implications, not only for individual rights but for society as a whole. This underscores the continuing importance of seeking multidisciplinary solutions to address these evolving challenges.